

THE CONSTITUTION IS A GUARANTEE OF CITIZENS' RIGHTS

Sh.Kh.Mamatalieva,

Lecturer of the Department of Criminal and Procedural Law of Tashkent

State Law University, Tashkent, Republic of Uzbekistan

Phone number: +99 890 985 89 80

Annotation. The rule of law is interrelated with the concepts of people's power and Human Rights, in which such rights as people's power, the right of citizens to participate directly or indirectly in the decision-making process, have taken place. Laws adopted by citizens through elected representatives of the parliament or by themselves directly through a referendum are the fruit of, figuratively speaking, the result of people's power. Human rights and freedoms are introduced to life through laws, in fact, the ultimate goal of laws is also an expression from the protection of man, his rights and freedoms.

Keywords: Constitution, rule of law, human benefit, protection of rights.

The preamble to the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan states that the people of Uzbekistan intend to build a state governed by the rule of law. An important and integral feature of the law is rule of law.

The rule of law is a principle directly related to the concepts of people's power and human rights. Because people's power means the right of citizens to participate directly or indirectly in the decision-making process. In this sense, laws that are the expression of the will of the people, adopted by citizens through their elected representatives in parliament or by direct referendum. Human rights and freedom are realized through laws in fact, the ultimate goal of laws is to protect man, his rights and freedoms.

Legislation as a key of the rule of law in international instruments is based on the rule of law, which includes transparency, accountability and a democratic process; legal clarity; prohibition of arbitrariness; openness of independent and impartial justice; as well as the establishment of judicial control over

administrative documents; respect and non-discrimination of human rights and equality before the law. The necessary normative-legal and organizational institutional bases of ensuring the rule of law have been formed in our country.

Chapter III of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan is entitled "The Constitution and the rule of law" and this chapter is located in the section of Basic Principles of the Constitution. It is clear from theory that principle refers to guidelines. If there is any misunderstanding between the other sections of the Constitution, the matter should be resolved in the basis of basic principles in theory. In this sense, the fact that the rule of law is settled in the section of Basic Principles shows that in our country this principle is given special attention.

The analysis of the provisions enshrined in this chapter and other norms of the Constitution leads to the following points: firstly, the supremacy of the Constitution and laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan is unconditionally recognized in the Republic of Uzbekistan. Secondly, the state, its bodies, officials, public associations, and citizens act in accordance with the Constitution and laws. Thirdly, no law or other normative legal act may contradict the norms and rules of the Constitution.

In addition, the organizational and legal framework for ensuring the rule of law and the rule of law has created in our country. Firstly, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan is the guarantor of the rights and freedoms of citizens, the Constitution and laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Parliamentary, public and administrative control over the implementation of laws, to what extent the court's activities are aimed at ensuring the rule of law, the protection of the rights and freedoms of each person through the courts, government agencies, officials.

Our legislation also defines legal instruments such as legal expertise, the system of impact assessment of legislation, monitoring, registration of departmental

documents, which are also important elements of ensuring the rule of law and the rule of law.

In many law fields, the rule of law is clarified as the main principles and tasks of ensuring the rule of law. For example, Article 2 of the Law on Internal Affairs states that one of the main tasks of law enforcement agencies is to ensure the rule of law. Article 6 of Law of internal affairs officers stipulates that must strictly observe and comply with the requirements of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, this Law and other legislation in their activities. Any deviation from the strict observance and observance of the laws, regardless of the reasons, is a violation of the rule of law and entails liability. In order to justify their unlawful actions (inaction) in the performance of their duties, law enforcement officers maybe interested in the interests of the service, economic expediency, unlawful demands, orders and directives of higher officials or any other unlawful act. -cannot avoid a situation. Direct or indirect incitement, persuasion or incitement of law enforcement officers to commit illegal acts is prohibited.

Article II of the Law on the Prosecutor's Office states that one of the main tasks of the prosecutor's office is to ensure the rule of law and strengthen the rule of law. Article VI of this law states that any deviation from the strict observance and observance of the law, regardless of the grounds on which it is made, is a violation of the law and entails liability.

Paragraph 1 of the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 19, 2017 No PR-2733 "On measures to radically improve the activities of the legal service" the organization of the rule of law and the rule of law in the law enforcement activities of organizations.

In addition, in order to ensure the rule of law is not only in government agencies, but also in each neighborhood. The Regulation on the public structure "Mahalla posboni" of the Citizens' Assembly, approved by the Cabinet of

Ministers on March 4, 2014 in cooperation with law enforcement officers, they are tasked with ensuring the rule of law, ensuring compliance with the rules of conduct and ethical standards in society, and assisting law enforcement officers in establishing order in the region.

Tasks related to ensuring the rule of law as one of the important issues in the Action Strategy for the five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2017-2021, approved by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PR-4947 dated February 7, 2017 shown.

The rule of law allows a person to exercise his rights and freedoms without hindrance, to guarantee his life, liberty, honor, dignity and other inalienable rights by law. The rule of law also stipulates that a person must participate in the adoption of these documents, which are binding on him or her through his or her elected representatives, influence public administration, exercise public control over the activities of public authorities, judicial protection of their rights and freedoms, the right to appeal to the court against the illegal actions of state bodies, officials, public associations. If the rule of law is not ensured in society, people will lose confidence not only in today, but also in tomorrow, and justice, equality and freedom will not be observed. In a society where the rule of law is not guaranteed, the economy will not develop and economic reforms will not be effective. Because no one wants to put their property, their sky, in a place where the law does not work. In a state where the rule of law prevails, freedom, justice, equality are guaranteed, the influence of power on the individual is limited, human rights are protected, property rights are respected, justice is independent and effective. Therefore, in the rankings compiled by various international organizations, research centers, special attention is paid to the rule of law. For example, The World Justice Project, an international non-governmental organization, conducts a special annual "Rule of Law Index" around the world. In the Transformation Index, the Bertelsmann International Foundation, and the World Bank's Public Administration Quality Indices, the rule of law is one of

the indicators of well-being. The laws on administrative courts and administrative procedures that are planned to be adopted are also important in ensuring the rule of law.

In short, the rule of law is a strong guarantee of freedom, justice, equality in society, protection of human rights, the formation of strong confidence in entrepreneurs and foreign investors for the sustainable growth of the country's economy.

REFERENCES:

1. Odilqoriyev X.T. Konstitutsiya va barkamol jamiyat orzusi. -T.: O‘qituvchi, 2012.
2. <http://www.gov.uz> (O‘zbekiston Respublikasi hukumati Portali)
3. O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Konstitutsiyasi. –T.: “O‘zbekiston” nashriyot –matbaa ijodiy uyi, -2020. -B. 13.
4. <http://www.parliament.gov.uz> (Oliy Majlis Qonunchilik palatasi).